

THE INFLUENCE OF PARENT-CHILD RELATIONSHIP ON THE FORMATION OF CHILDREN'S BEHAVIOR

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Abstract. This article covers the topic of the influence of parents and children on the formation of children's behavior, in which the analysis of the scientific and theoretical views of pedagogues and psychologists on the topic of the role of parents in the family and its psychological influence on the formation of children's behavior, as well as the conclusion and recommendations are written.

Key words: family, parents, child, behavior, psychological influence, education, girls, boys, formation.

From the 17th-18th centuries, the study of the relationship between parents and children, and the issues of raising children in the family as a subject of special scientific research, began to be widely carried out. According to L.Stone, between 1750 and 1814, more than 2,400 books with the same title were published in England alone. Family life, parent-child relationship has been the subject of special research for ethnologists and scientists of other fields in the last hundred years. A number of works have been created in addition to studies devoted to the study of the relationship between parents and children in the families of one or another nation, nation and region.

In this place, a significant part of the activities of E.Taylor, S.Leurno, E.Westermark, D.Frazer, G.Ploss and other scientists is dedicated to this issue. Also, in Western psychological literature, the formation of parent-child relationships, the influence of children's interpersonal relationships in the family on the behavior of the child's personality, and how these characteristics are manifested in children who are raised outside the family compared with their cases and analyzed the causes of a number of differences.

Parents have different approaches to child rearing. There are also three main models of "parental" behavior, and psychologist D. Baumrind explained these models as follows:

1. Liberal model
2. Authoritarian model.

For complete information, let's take a closer look at how each model affects a child's personality development and communication skills. According to the collected opinions and comments, the liberal model cannot develop self-

confidence in child education. Parents who belong to the liberal model are indifferent to the child and do not take special care of the child from a young age. In most cases, parents who belong to this model leave the child to fend for themselves, such children often feel that they are not needed by anyone. Parents who choose the authoritarian model pay little attention to showing affection and kindness in raising their children. They pay more attention to order - discipline, strictness in raising a child. Rather than having a friendly relationship with the child, having a heart-to-heart conversation, understanding him, talking about his interests, they act more on the basis of their interests and desires. According to them, this method of upbringing will raise the child as a "real person". Authoritarian parents are interested in the opinions of others about their children. Excessive demands in the educational process instills insecurity in the child, which in itself causes the child to be disappointed and internal tension in the child. Father and mother always decide everything for their child, do not trust and allow the child to independently perform one or another task, extinguish his will and self-confidence, look at the child as a person who always fulfills the assigned tasks, and mentally destroy the child. lack of support makes the child angry, irritable, nervous or, on the contrary, passive, useless, lonely. As a result of studying the influence of these models on children, Dr. D. Braumrind came to the conclusion that the most effective and comfortable model among the models is the model of authority. Parents who approve of this model have an objective idea about the child's abilities at each age, they regularly communicate with their children and take their opinions into account. Such parents are not afraid to change the decisions they have made and the directions of upbringing, because they take into account the psychological and physiological characteristics of the child. Some mistakes made in the relationship with the child in the process of upbringing can become serious problems in his future life when the child grows up. Some problems, difficulties and misunderstandings can also arise as a result of parents' shallow ideas about child education. The fact is that in most cases, parents do not take into account their child's unique characteristics, abilities, inclinations and desires in the process of education. They often bring up a child according to the direction they think, adapting to a certain "pattern" and with a certain result in mind. In our opinion, the task of the parents is to accept the positive and negative sides of the child and encourage the positive aspects in him. The only way to successfully implement education is to raise a child not only with knowledge, but with love from the heart. Good parenting means good attitude. This, in turn, requires the ability to feel what is

going on in the child's heart, to correctly understand the reasons for his actions and behavior, and to assess him adequately. Some mistakes made in the relationship with the child during the upbringing process can become a serious problem in the child's future life when he grows up.

A.N. Leontiev, A.R. Luria, D.B. Elkonin and others showed that the child's mental development is determined by the features of his emotional connection and cooperation with parents. The dynamics of family life and the nature of the emotional relationship of parents to a child are important for the formation of his personality and behavior. At all stages of the child's development in the family, he is constantly influenced by various factors of the family environment, including the style of family upbringing. It can have both a healing effect on the family's educational function and a destabilizing effect that creates various problems for the family, its members, and the environment. Research conducted by D.V. Berko and according to Berko's words in it, upbringing styles affect the formation of personality, which is manifested at the level of characteristics, personal maturity and the semantic structure of everyday consciousness. Thus, at the trait level, a significant correlation was established between the educational principles of both parents and the personality structures responsible for psychological health, emotional state, behavior regulation, and the level of social adaptation. Girls were more sensitive to the aggressive style of maternal leadership. At the level of characteristics, this is expressed by an increase in the level of aggression, which creates the prerequisites for impulsive behavior. At the level of everyday consciousness - when the opposite picture of the world appears, when the image of the mother is presented as "good", but disgusting. The father's role played a crucial role in girls' acceptance of self-realization values, female identity and instrumental values that enable them to realize their goals and protect their interests. The father's directive style has the greatest effect on the productive state of daughters (increased depression level, lability of emotional states). Girls who negatively evaluate the educational principles of both parents have cognitive complexity, which provides neurotic protection of the personality. The father's negative attitude leads to the formation of specific defensive reactions in girls that make them want to fight.

In their research, A. Ya. Varga and V. V. Stolin identified the following criteria of parental relations: "Acceptance - rejection." Acceptance: The parent loves the child the way he is. He respects the child's individuality, sympathizes with him. Denial: the parent sees his child as bad, unacceptable, unsuccessful, often feels anger, discomfort, anger, resentment towards the child. He does not

trust the child, does not respect him. "Cooperation" - the parent is interested in the child's work and plans, tries to help him in everything. He appreciates his intellectual and creative abilities, feels proud of him. "Symbiosis" - the parent always feels concern for the child, he seems small and defenseless to him. Parents do not give independence to the child. "Authoritarian hypersocialization" - the parent demands unconditional obedience and discipline from the child. He tries to impose his will on him in everything, the child is severely punished for the manifestation of his will. The parent closely monitors the child's social behavior and demands social success. "Little loser" - there is a desire in parental relations to infantilize the child, to associate him with personal and social incompetence. The child seems maladjusted, unsuccessful, open to bad influences. An adult tries to protect the child from the difficulties of life and strictly controls his actions.

Differences in the attitude of the father and the mother to the child have attracted the attention of many researchers. E. Fromm writes about the differences between maternal and paternal love, as love angers different personalities. In his opinion, paternal love is "demanding" compared to maternal love, and in order to develop it, a child must be served. Fatherly love is not born, but is formed in the early years of the child. In order to be worthy of the father's love, the child must meet certain social requirements and the abilities, achievements, and successes set by the father. Love is served as a reward for success and good behavior. For that reason, the child has the opportunity to continue the generation, because in accordance with traditional norms, a free heir must be brought up as a successor of the generation, a keeper of traditions and memory. In this way, the family fulfills its social theoretical function and is the owner of the demands of discipline and sanctions (measures to be taken). A mother's love is a genealogy as opposed to a family's. According to A. Adler, the mother's role in education is to encourage activities aimed at developing social competence (competence). If the mother allows the child to feel the sociality of human love, the father paves the way for the child to human society.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the father is a source of knowledge for children about the world, local technology, helps them to form socially useful goals and ideals, and helps them in their professional orientation. A mother's love provides the opportunity to receive, while a father's care encourages a return. It is necessary for personal development. It is important to study the features of interaction of parents with children of different ages when analyzing

the difference between the influence of fathers and mothers in the development of the child and the formation of his behavior.

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